

Tangent of two circles

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Let us discuss a simple geometrical problem. In the figure, both circles and the tangent are shown. The quadrangle has two right angles. The other angles are β and δ .

r_1, r_2 = radii of the two circles

We search for p . Only the both radii are known.

$$\beta = 360^\circ - 2 \cdot 90^\circ - \delta = 180^\circ - \delta$$

We apply the law of cosines and the Pythagoras theorem:

$$p^2 + r_1^2 = r_2^2 + (r_1 + r_2)^2 - 2r_2 \cdot (r_1 + r_2) \cdot \cos \delta \quad (1)$$

$$r_2^2 + p^2 = (r_1 + r_2)^2 + r_1^2 - 2r_1 \cdot (r_1 + r_2) \cdot \cos \beta \quad (2)$$

$$\cos \beta = \cos(180^\circ - \delta) = -\cos \delta$$

It follows:

$$r_2^2 + p^2 = (r_1 + r_2)^2 + r_1^2 + 2r_1 \cdot (r_1 + r_2) \cdot \cos \delta \quad (3)$$

Resolving (1) and (3) for $\cos \delta$ and equating:

$$\frac{r_2^2 + (r_1 + r_2)^2 - r_1^2 - p^2}{2r_2 \cdot (r_1 + r_2)} = \frac{r_2^2 + p^2 - r_1^2 - (r_1 + r_2)^2}{2r_1 \cdot (r_1 + r_2)}$$

reduction:

$$\frac{2 \cdot (r_2^2 + r_1 r_2) - p^2}{r_2} = \frac{p^2 - 2 \cdot (r_1^2 + r_1 r_2)}{r_1}$$

multiplying out:

$$2r_1 \cdot (r_2^2 + r_1 r_2) - p^2 r_1 = r_2 p^2 - 2r_2 \cdot (r_1^2 + r_1 r_2)$$

transformation:

$$2r_1 \cdot (r_2^2 + r_1 r_2) + 2r_2 \cdot (r_1^2 + r_1 r_2) = p^2 \cdot (r_1 + r_2)$$

$$2 \cdot (r_2^2 r_1 + r_1^2 r_2 + r_1^2 r_2 + r_1 r_2^2) = p^2 \cdot (r_1 + r_2)$$

thus:

$$4 \cdot (r_1^2 r_2 + r_1 r_2^2) = p^2 \cdot (r_1 + r_2)$$

Resolving for p :

$$p = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{r_1^2 r_2 + r_2^2 r_1}{r_1 + r_2}}$$

special cases:

With $r_1 = r_2 = r$ we obtain $p = 2r$.

With r_1 or $r_2 = 0$ we get $p = 0$ and the tangent of one circle.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001